

The Importance of Artificial Intelligence Technologies in Developing the Skills of Social Workers

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ABSTRACT: Artificial intelligence (AI) is redefining how people work, yet in Saudi Arabia its role in social work remains understudied. This study relied on a cross-sectional design to evaluate how students and faculty members in Saudi Arabian social work departments perceive AI's potential in improving skill development, the extent to which social work departments support AI education, and the risks linked to its adoption. A structured questionnaire was administered to 390 participants from Saudi Arabian higher education institutions. The study results revealed participants' recognition of AI's utility in improving social work education and practice, while highlighting low personal competency and inadequate departmental action. Moreover, participants expressed strong concerns about job displacement and ethical risks associated with AI applications in social work.

Key words: Artificial Intelligence, Social Work Education, AI Adoption, Skill Development, AI Risks

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1. Introduction

Over the last decade, Artificial intelligence (AI) has transitioned from being a largely theoretical concept confined to research circles into becoming “one of the most important and formative technologies today” (Tjoa et al., 2022, p.72). In this context, AI refers to computer systems that can solve problems and learn through different modalities with the goal of simulating human intelligence (Aboalshamat et al., 2022). The primary defining feature of AI is its ability to perform specific functions that were historically reserved for humans (Dwivedi et al., 2021). For this reason, AI is expected and is being positioned to shape human activity, with the most significant changes expected to be in how humans work and learn. It is widely accepted that AI will increasingly boost the productivity and efficiency of workers, resulting in improved outcomes in the workplace and society (Muafa et al., 2024). Thus, AI is being embedded into various sectors of the economy, such as healthcare, finance, education, and even social governance (Dwivedi et al., 2021). As a result, one can expect AI to become the transformative force that helps improve all the above-mentioned sectors of society.

In Saudi Arabia, the shift towards adopting AI fits within the country's larger digitization agenda. The Kingdom continues to invest in digital innovation as part of its Vision 2030, prioritizing technologies that can enhance business, governance, education,

and public welfare (Woishi, 2019). Woishi (2019) further noted that Saudi Arabia has placed a strong focus on getting the labor market ready for digitization, with human beings working hand-in-hand with computer systems, optimizing value generation, while increasing business agility.

However, discussions about the application of AI in the economy have mostly focused on sectors such as healthcare, engineering, governmental services, and business innovation (Woishi, 2019). There is minimal attention devoted to the functions that AI can serve in social work service delivery and in how social workers develop their skills. Given that social workers are at the frontline actors of addressing complex societal issues such as poverty, community development, family stability, and child protection, the use of AI and other digital technologies could have a significant positive impact on Saudi society.

Although the social work profession, due to its grounding in human relationships and its reliance on social contexts and ethical values, might initially seem like a field that could not benefit from emerging technologies, it has a lot to gain from AI. For instance, AI can help social workers to become more efficient in administrative work, pattern identification, understanding of client populations, and timely diagnoses (Toli & Manasa, 2024). AI can also enhance social workers' case management and decision-making, resulting in enhanced service delivery (Li et al., 2025). These promises make AI a desirable tool for social workers.

Despite these opportunities, the idea of integrating AI and other digital technologies into social work presents various challenges. Case in point, the use of AI in social work raises ethical questions about the privacy of personal data, potential biases, and the risk of technology eliminating the nuanced contextual understanding of client situations, humanistic care, and ethical judgment that define social work (Chen & Lin, 2025). Rodríguez-Martínez et al. (2024) further asserted that digital technologies could weaken the concept of informed consent within social work practice. These are all serious concerns that cannot be ignored.

At the same time, it is unclear whether social workers are prepared and willing to incorporate AI in their profession. In Saudi Arabia, it is also not clear if social work departments at universities are well equipped to teach AI competencies to students and whether they have the resources to achieve this goal. This situation raises questions about the part that social work departments' faculty members and students have to play in influencing the fate of AI use in their profession.

The current study builds upon these questions and seeks to evaluate how AI can impact the development of social workers' skills in Saudi Arabia. Instead of solely focusing on what is possible technically, this study evaluated how faculty members in social work departments view the role of AI in practice as well as its risks, and the role of their university departments in educating students about AI's role in social work.

Artificial Intelligence in Saudi Arabia

AI has been incorporated into Saudi Arabia's national transformation agenda, as part of efforts to grow and diversify the economy and increase the effectiveness of public services. Saudi Arabia's Vision 2030 recognizes the role of modern technologies in

unlocking the potential of Saudi Arabia's non-oil sectors by developing human capital (Memish et al., 2021). In 2019, Saudi Arabia formally recognized the role that AI will play in its economy and established the Saudi Data and Artificial Intelligence Authority (SDAIA), with the mandate of supporting and driving the development and adoption of Big Data and AI technology and positioning the country as a leading data-driven economy (Memish et al., 2021). To achieve these goals, the SDAIA set up the National Center for Artificial Intelligence (NCAI). The NCAI is an operational arm tasked with conducting Saudi's AI research and development, offering government agencies strategic AI advisory, building collaborations with academia and the private sector, supporting independent AI research within the country, and promoting the development of AI use cases (Memish et al., 2021). Therefore, there is a tangible commitment and support for AI development from the Saudi Arabian government.

The adoption of AI in Saudi Arabia is most notable in healthcare and education. First, AI adoption in healthcare is partly attributable to the NCAI's determination that healthcare is a priority sector, with AI expected to enable healthcare professionals meet the growing needs of the Saudi population (Aljehani & Al Naweess, 2025). Aljehani and Al Naweess (2025) supported the preceding assertions by pointing out that AI systems are currently being applied for predictive diagnostics, clinical decision support, analysis of electronic health records, and the curation of personalized treatment plans. Although the input of healthcare workers still be needed in practice, as is the case with social work, there is no doubt that the Saudi Arabian healthcare sector benefits from the effective integration of AI to improve clinical outcomes, minimize wait times, and optimize the use of scarce medical resources.

Saudi Arabia's education sector is also attracting significant attention and activity in AI adoption. Saudi's Vision 2030 targets to transform education by integrating technology. As a result, this has allowed ambitious AI-powered technology, such as smart tutoring systems and AI-powered virtual classrooms, to gain widespread acceptance in the country (Al-Motrif, 2025). These AI-powered pedagogy systems make the education sector more efficient by enhancing teaching effectiveness, optimizing administrative processes, and enabling personalized learning that caters to the specific needs of individual students (Al-Motrif, 2025). More significantly, the government's commitment to AI adoption has been demonstrated by recent integrations of AI as part of the curriculum. Beginning with the 2025-2026 academic year, the SDAIA, in cooperation with the Saudi National Center for Curriculum, the Ministry of Education, and the Ministry of Communication and Information Technology, has developed an AI curriculum for the six million general school students in the Kingdom (Saudi Press Agency [SPA], 2025). This new curriculum intends to help students understand the important role that AI plays and to equip them with the skills and competencies needed to develop AI-based solutions for everyday problems (SPA, 2025). The above changes demonstrate how the education sector can benefit from AI while also acting as a gateway for other sectors to benefit from the technology.

The Role of Artificial Intelligence in Social Work

Although social work is a fundamentally human-centered discipline, it is also being gradually reshaped by AI. AI is introducing tools that support decision-making, simplify administrative tasks for social workers, and enhance overall service delivery (Pazer,

2024). Minguijon and Serrano-Martinez (2022) stated that in social work, AI functions primarily to augment the work of employees, supporting the tasks where social workers could benefit from computational assistance in order to enhance their productivity and efficiency, in terms of time and costs. Hence, this shows that AI is not intended to replace social workers.

One of the most notable contributions of AI in social work is its ability to enhance the efficiency of administrative tasks. Minguijon and Serrano-Martinez (2022) pointed out that social workers face overwhelming bureaucratic demands, such as registering actions carried out with their clients, verification of requirements for access to services, and recording of decisions related to granting or denying benefits to clients. The activities described above create high workloads and stress, leading to potential burnout. Hence, AI-powered automation tools can minimize the time spent on such administrative tasks like data entry, documentation, and report writing, creating additional time for social workers to engage their clients (Minguijon & Serrano-Martinez, 2022). Social workers are, therefore, able to manage large caseloads without compromising the quality of service offered to clients.

Additionally, AI introduces multiple possibilities into the field of social work. Reamer (2023) explained these new possibilities, noting that AI's ability to process large datasets facilitates predictive analytics where collected data is used to forecast challenges and successes of service, enabling social workers to determine the best way to allocate resources. For instance, AI-powered predictive analysis has been used to predict risks of going through social problems, such as the risk of child abuse and need for intervention, as well as the risk of recidivism in the criminal justice system (Asakura et al., 2020; Reamer, 2023). This predictive analysis equips social workers with indispensable data-driven insights that they would otherwise not have.

Another useful prospect with AI is its ability to improve case management. AI-powered systems can analyze client records, identify risk factors, flag cases that need intervention, classify interventions, and monitor services (Li et al., 2025). Such systems reduce decision bias, improve decision-making, make service delivery more cost-effective, and allow the expansion of social work to cover more clients (Li et al., 2025; Pazer, 2024). Therefore, the use of AI in case management provides the opportunity for social work to have an expanded impact on society.

Beyond these major AI applications, there are other assorted use cases for AI in social work. These use cases include chatbots that offer social services such as mental health support, AI-powered virtual therapy, the analysis and evaluation of social programs, powering community organizations, and promoting the professional development of social workers (Kumar & Singh, 2023).

However, AI integration into social work practice also raises ethical and practical challenges that are hard to ignore. There are concerns that AI could undercut the human-centered ethos of social work by over-relying on technology, malfunction, and cause unpredictable damage, put the privacy and confidentiality of client data at risk, and reduce the scope of individualized and context-sensitive interventions (Kumar & Singh, 2023; Pazer, 2024). There are also concerns that social workers are inadequately prepared to incorporate AI in their work and have been insufficiently exposed to this technology

(Molala & Mbaya, 2023). Hence, the role that AI will play in social work requires a balance between technological innovation, the professional ethos of social work, and the training of social workers.

Study Aims

The main goal of the study was to assess AI's current contribution to social workers' skills development in Saudi Arabia, drawing on insights from faculty members and students in Saudi Arabian universities' social work departments. This primary aim was broken into three specific objectives. First, the study explored how AI is understood and applied in social work practice. Second, the study investigated the role social work departments in Saudi universities play and are expected to play in teaching students about AI and its use in social work. Finally, the study sought to analyze potential risks and challenges that are linked to AI application in social work.

Study Questions

The central research question for this study was: What role do artificial intelligence technologies play in developing the skills of social workers in Saudi Arabia? To comprehensively answer this primary question, the following secondary questions were used:

- 1) How well do social workers in Saudi Arabia understand the role that AI plays in the social work?
- 2) What is the role of social work departments in teaching AI competency to social work students?
- 3) What are the risks and challenges linked to using AI in social work?

The Importance of the Study

The findings from this study will contribute to the understanding of how the social work profession is responding to emerging technology such as AI. While AI adoption has been widely studied in other sectors of society, such as healthcare, education, and business, its application in social work has received minimal scholarly attention. In Saudi Arabia, this scholarly attention is almost nonexistent. Given Saudi Arabia's ongoing digital transformation and the explicit commitment by the government to promote the application of AI into key sectors of the economy (Memish et al., 2021), this study offers important insight into whether universities are effectively preparing social workers for the reality of a work environment where AI use is promoted.

From a practical point of view, this study is critical as it could provide useful insights that could help enhance the preparedness of social workers in Saudi Arabia and other settings to operate within an AI-ready environment. Social workers play an irreplaceable role in addressing complex social issues and often face heavy workloads and administrative demands. Since AI adoption could make their work easier and more effective, it is important to determine if they understand the role AI could play in their work, their level of acceptance of AI, and whether their universities are imparting them with AI competency skills.

The study also offers insights into the risks and challenges that social workers anticipate in the adoption of AI systems in their work. These insights will provide a nuanced understanding of the readiness and resistance within social work education and establish how students and faculty members view the relationship between AI and the ethos of social work. In a nutshell, this study explores the bottlenecks in social work education that might be holding back social workers' AI competencies in the Saudi Arabian context and provide initial recommendations on what the future should look like for social work training.

Study Concepts

Social Work

Social work is a field that focuses to improving the overall well-being of society by taking action at the individual, family, and community level (Kumar & Singh, 2023). Social work, therefore, combines theory and practice to address and solve societal issues such as poverty, mental health issues, family instability, and discrimination that cause difficulty for people. Social work demands a unique review of how it interacts with technology in practice because of its human-centric nature. In social work, success is significantly tied to forming trusted relationships with clients to facilitate the voluntary flow of information. However, Molala and Mbaya (2023) argued that while it might be impossible for AI to completely eliminate social workers, it is beneficial to fuse social work with AI and to train social workers on how to use AI, and consequently have well-rounded professionals. This is the lens through which this study views social work, hence the exploration of how AI is being taught in social work departments.

Artificial Intelligence

Artificial intelligence is an emerging technology that changes how human beings interact with computers. AI refers to advanced computer systems that complete cognitive tasks that are traditionally associated with human minds (Asakura et al., 2020). These tasks include learning, problem-solving, reasoning, and decision-making, and are powered by various technologies and computational processes (Dwivedi et al., 2021). AI has wide applicability across different sectors, including social work. This applicability in social work and the perceptions surrounding it are the subject of inquiry for this study.

Risk Management

In the context of this study, risk management refers to the process of acknowledging the existence of, identifying, assessing, and mitigating potential threats and challenges that are associated with significant changes within a profession. For workers, risk from AI are associated with the possibility of being replaced in the workplace (Deranty & Corbin, 2022). However, Reamer (2023) posited that for social workers, this risk mostly manifests in terms of how AI could shape the outcomes of work and interact with the professional ethics and principles of social work, such as maintaining data privacy and client confidentiality. One of the goals of this study is to establish how social work faculty members and students perceive this risk and respond to it.

2. Methodology of the Study

Method

This study adopted a descriptive-analytical design with the aim of giving an in-depth description of the importance of AI in advancing the skills of social workers in Saudi Arabia based on the views of faculty members and students in social work. This methodological approach was suited for the study as it sought to examine three different variables that define the state of AI incorporation in the development of social workers. These variables include how AI is understood within social work practice by students and faculty members, the extent to which social work departments have incorporated AI into their curriculum and in their teaching, and the risks that social work students and faculty members in Saudi Arabia associate with AI adoption in social work.

Data were systematically collected using a social survey conducted on participants who were involved in social work education. Following the collection of data, descriptive analyses were performed to identify patterns and relationships related to how AI is perceived and understood within the Saudi Arabian social work profession.

Study Population and Sample

The study's population included university faculty members and students in social work departments across higher education institutions in Saudi Arabia. This population was targeted because it is directly engaged in social work education, research, and practice, and can therefore provide a useful inside look of how AI is integrated into the social work field. Moreover, both faculty members and students were included in the survey to ensure that the perspectives of both trainers and their trainees were captured. Random sampling was adopted for the study to reduce bias and ensure representativeness, which culminated in a sample size of 390 participants.

Study Tools

The main data collection instrument used was a structured questionnaire that had a three-point Likert scale. The questionnaire consisted of three different sections, each measuring a different dimension: a section on the participants' understanding of the role of AI in the profession, a section on the role that social work departments play in teaching AI competency, and section on the risks and challenges linked to AI adoption in social work practice.

To establish the questionnaire's content validity, six academic experts from Saudi universities were invited to review it and provide feedback that informed revisions to its initial draft. A pilot study with a sample of 18 was carried out to test the reliability of the questionnaire. The questionnaire had a Cronbach's alpha of 0.97, which, based on Taber's (2018) findings, is considered an excellent rating. The instrument used was therefore deemed to be both valid and reliable for its intended purpose.

Table 1: Understanding the Role of AI in Social Work

N	Items	Response	F	%	Mean	SD	Rank
1	I can use artificial intelligence.	Always	72	18.5	2.31	1.108	1
		Sometimes	126	32.3			
		Scarcely	192	49.2			
2	I can use artificial intelligence in relation to social work.	Always	57	14.6	2.30	0.993	2
		Sometimes	158	40.4			
		Scarcely	175	45.0			
3	I know that artificial intelligence contributes to developing the skills of social workers.	Always	71	18.1	2.30	1.081	3
		Sometimes	186	47.7			
		Scarcely	133	34.2			
4	I know that artificial intelligence helps in conducting social studies.	Always	71	18.1	2.26	1.029	4
		Sometimes	148	38.1			
		Scarcely	171	43.8			
5	I know that artificial intelligence contributes to providing social solutions.	Always	86	21.9	2.25	1.128	5
		Sometimes	121	31.2			
		Scarcely	183	46.9			
6	I know that artificial intelligence contributes to the effectiveness of social workers' work.	Always	81	20.8	2.23	1.075	6
		Sometimes	137	35.0			
		Scarcely	172	44.2			
The overall mean of participants' understanding of the role of AI in social work.					2.16	1.09	

Table 1 presents participants' perceptions about their ability to understand and use AI in social work practice and in the development of skills needed for social work. The overall mean score of 2.16 indicates that respondents have a modest level of understanding of the role that AI plays in social work. For all six items making up this section of the questionnaire, the majority of responses clustered around "sometimes" and "scarcely," with the combined frequency of these two responses ranging from 78.1% to 85.4%, suggesting an inconsistent and generally low engagement with AI tools among the respondents.

It is worth noting that, the highest-rated statement was "I can use artificial intelligence" (mean = 2.31, SD = 1.108), indicating that participants generally have interacted with AI at the personal level. Closely following this top statement was the item measuring personal use of AI for work ("I can use artificial intelligence in relation to social

work.”) with a mean score of 2.30. These results indicate that not only faculty members and students interacted with AI at the personal level, they have used it in social work contexts. The item measuring AI’s contribution to developing social workers’ skills also got a mean score of 2.30, indicating that participants not only used AI for social work, but they also understood that AI contributes to their skill development.

On the other hand, the three questionnaire items measuring AI’s utility in practice: helping in conducting social studies (2.26); providing social solutions (2.25); and bolstering the effectiveness of social work (2.23) had comparable means, which were slightly lower, as shown above. This indicates some skepticism towards the practical contributions of AI towards social work. At the same time, the moderate mean scores demonstrate that the participants understand that AI could be useful in practice and for training purposes. It is also notable that the mean standard deviation is considerably low at 1.09. This indicates low variance in the perceptions of the participants. Hence, this could be linked to even exposure to AI across different institutions.

Thus, these findings highlight social work professionals’ moderate personal competence in AI and recognition of the utility of AI in social work, which could be reinvigorated if social work programs in Saudi Arabian universities provide structured, practical training about AI and its applications in social work. Failure to do this would risk the field of social work falling behind in adapting to a technology that is already transforming other fields, such as healthcare.

Table 2: Comprehending the Role of Social Work Departments in Teaching Artificial Intelligence.

N	Items	Response	F	%	Mean	SD	Rank
1	Social work departments should teach artificial intelligence.	Agree	206	52.7	2.38	1.092	1
		To some extent	129	33.1			
		Disagree	55	14.2			
2	Social work departments encourage teaching artificial intelligence.	Agree	63	16.2	2.32	1.053	2
		To some extent	141	36.2			
		Disagree	186	47.7			
3	Artificial intelligence education is essential for social workers.	Agree	164	41.9	2.29	0.923	3
		To some extent	177	45.4			
		Disagree	49	12.7			
4		Agree	177	45.4	2.29	1.022	4

	Social work departments are not interested in artificial intelligence.	To some extent	150	38.5			
		Disagree	63	16.2			
5	Social work departments offer workshops on artificial intelligence.	Agree	51	13.1	2.27	0.898	5
		To some extent	155	39.6			
		Disagree	184	47.3			
6	Social workers are trained in artificial intelligence through social work departments.	Agree	90	23.1	2.25	1.161	6
		To some extent	113	28.8			
		Disagree	187	48.1			
The overall mean of participants' comprehension of the role of social work departments in teaching artificial intelligence.				2.24	1.061		

Table 2 above presents participants' views on the role of social work departments in campuses in teaching about AI and how it can be applied in social work. The highest-rated item in this section was "Social work departments should teach artificial intelligence" ($M = 2.38$, $SD = 1.092$). The participants' recognition that "Artificial intelligence education is essential for social workers" ($M = 2.29$, $SD = 0.923$) also reinforce this outcome, positioning AI competency as a key part of professional preparedness for social work in today's world.

Notably, the item "Social work departments are not interested in artificial intelligence" also received a relatively high mean score of 2.29, suggesting that there was a perception that social work departments were unwilling to adapt and incorporate AI in their curriculum. This perceived institutional inertia is further given credence by the lower scores on "Social work departments offer workshops on artificial intelligence" ($M = 2.27$), and "Social workers are trained in artificial intelligence through social work departments" ($M = 2.25$). These scores indicate that there is minimal departmental engagement in AI. The results mean that there is unsatisfactory implementation of AI teaching in social work departments, despite there being a consensus that this teaching is needed. However, there does seem to be some form of goodwill from social work departments, as demonstrated by the more moderate score on the item "Social work departments encourage teaching artificial intelligence" ($M = 2.32$). This could indicate that even though social work departments are not proactive in creating initiatives that promote AI adoption, they communicate support for AI teaching.

Taken together, the results indicate a clear disconnect between the expectations placed on social work departments and the efforts put in by departments to teach and promote AI. This gap has to be addressed if social workers are to be introduced to AI while in institutions of higher learning. Addressing this gap, on the other hand, requires strategic

investment and effort by social work departments to adjust their curricula and provide practical training opportunities for both students and faculty members.

Table 3: Participants' Perception of the Risks of Using Artificial Intelligence in Social Work

N	Items	Response	Frequency	%	Mean	SD	Rank
1	What is the difficulty level of learning artificial intelligence?	High	48	12.3	2.39	1.047	1
		Medium	141	36.2			
		Low	201	51.5			
2	What are the level of risks of artificial intelligence	High	189	48.5	2.37	0.994	2
		Medium	156	40.0			
		Low	45	11.5			
3	How likely is it that artificial intelligence will replace the role of social workers?	High	185	47.3	2.34	1.002	3
		Medium	154	39.6			
		Low	51	13.1			
4	What is the level of threat artificial intelligence poses to job opportunities for social workers?	High	188	48.1	2.32	1.058	4
		Medium	139	35.8			
		Low	63	16.2			
5	How likely is it that artificial intelligence will be able to solve social problems?	High	78	20.0	2.29	1.126	5
		Medium	122	31.2			
		Low	190	48.8			
6	How secure are artificial intelligence applications in social work?	High	77	19.6	2.28	1.110	6
		Medium	126	32.3			
		Low	187	48.1			
The overall mean of the participants' perception of the risks of using AI in social work					2.30	1.076	

Table 3 reports the participants' perceptions of the risks and challenges associated with the use of AI in social work. The table shows that the respondents generally perceive AI as having high risks, with a notable emphasis on threats to social workers' employment and professional roles. The question "What are the level of risks of artificial intelligence?" had a mean score of 2.37, indicating a collective view by the participants that AI carried significant risks for the social work profession in Saudi Arabia.

Closely following these perceived general risks was the concern about the specific risk of AI replacing the roles of social workers and even pushing them out of their jobs.

This concern is demonstrated by the items "How likely is it that artificial intelligence will replace the role of social workers?" and "What is the level of threat artificial intelligence poses to job opportunities for social workers?" Having mean scores of 2.34 and 2.32, respectively. These results highlight that professionals (and future professionals) in social work have anxieties that the integration of AI in social work could erode demand for them in social work practice.

At the same time, the participants also seem to have concerns about the security of AI when used for social work. As a result of these concerns, the item "How secure are AI applications in social work?" has a mean score of 2.28, with close to half of all participants (48.1%) stating that AI applications are low in security, and only 19.1% stating that these AI applications have high security. Additionally, the participants express skepticism about AI's ability to solve social problems, with 48.8% of all respondents stating that there is a low chance that AI is able to solve social issues. Interestingly, a majority of the participants (51.5%) reported that the difficulty level of learning AI is low, with only 12.3% indicating that this difficulty is high. This finding indicates that the participants do not consider technical difficulty as a primary barrier for AI adoption.

3. Discussion of the Results

The results of the current study paint a detailed picture of how social work professionals (current ones and future ones) in Saudi Arabia view AI and its role in the social work field. By analyzing participants' understanding of AI, the state of AI education in social work departments, and the perceived risks of AI, these findings can create a picture of the AI-adoption environment in Saudi Arabia, at least at the point where social workers are prepared for the workplace. The findings of the current study reveal both consistencies and divergences from extant literature on the state of AI use in social work.

The findings of this study clearly indicate that social workers in Saudi Arabia generally acknowledge that AI has, at the very least, some value in enhancing social work and the development of skills for social workers. These findings resoundingly resonate with extant research that supports the idea that AI solutions could improve social work and expand possibilities for service improvements in social work (Goldkind, 2021). The technological support for social work by AI is particularly needed, considering the overwhelming workloads that social workers deal with in a world where pressing issues that demand their attention are ever-expanding, while the resources available to them are barely enough (Nuwasiima et al., 2024). Additionally, social problems are increasingly becoming more complex, requiring extensive analysis of large sets of data in order to develop effective interventions (Nuwasiima et al., 2024). It is therefore not surprising that social workers in Saudi Arabia consider AI a source of improvement in their work.

However, recognizing the importance of AI does not translate to competence in using AI at the personal level. In fact, the participants only have moderate personal competence in AI and recognition of the utility of AI in social work, a situation that points towards a possible deficiency in the training that social workers receive while still in school. This deficiency can only be explained by there being social work programs in Saudi Arabian institutions that do not expose students to AI and its application in social work.

True to these speculations, further inquiry into the role that social work departments already play reveals that there is indeed a deficiency in exposure to AI. The results indicate

that departmental practice across social work departments in Saudi Arabia barely includes any training opportunities for students to learn about AI and its application in social work. There is also seemingly minimal interest by social work departments to explore this area of study and to educate their students on the same. This finding is consistent with Abolhasan's (2023) overall findings that many social work education programs lack a defined approach to prepare social workers to incorporate AI and other digital technologies in their practice.

However, the results indicate quite clearly that social work professionals in Saudi Arabia believe that teaching AI to students is part of the role of social work departments in universities, with only 14.2% of the participants disagreeing. These findings are aligned with the generally accepted idea that higher learning institutions have a responsibility to train their faculty members and students on the use of AI and other emerging technologies (Khan et al., 2025). Nuwasiima et al. (2024) further argue that, for social work departments specifically, training students on the integration of AI in practice and skill building is needed so as to equip these students with the requisite skills for effective practice and gradually build their skills even while in practice.

The results of the current study also reveal that there is some level of frustration among social work students and faculty members about the inaction of their departments on the issue of incorporating AI in the curriculum and the educational processes used. This frustration is clear from the strong agreement that respondents had with the statement that "social work departments are not interested in artificial intelligence". This inaction on AI is incompatible with a Saudi society where the government, as part of its Vision 2030, is encouraging the incorporation of AI and other technologies in various sectors (Al-Motrif, 2025). This lag in adopting AI could also be a testament to the unique concerns surrounding the social work sector adopting new digital technologies.

However, even though the participants show frustration with their departments for inaction, they themselves have clear concerns about the role that AI will play in social work. The participants strongly associate AI with risks, with the strongest risks being the threat that AI poses to their employment and professional roles. These concerns are understandable since the possibility of AI substituting human work is a common concern about this technology (Deranty & Corbin, 2022). However, there is a general agreement in the literature that AI cannot fully replace social workers due to the relational and ethical dimensions of this form of work (Abolhasan, 2023; Molala & Mbaya, 2023; Reamer, 2023). Therefore, this anxiety can be solved with education.

The more complex concerns that the participants identified are the concerns about the security of AI. These concerns are valid because even though AI systems can support some operations in social work, they are recognized to expose social work to risks around confidentiality, bias, the transparency of decisions, and the adherence to the ethical safeguards of the profession (Hodgson et al., 2022). Hodgson et al. (2022) further argue that it is important for social work professionals, particularly educators and researchers, to reflect on the ethical implications, challenges, and risks that come with applying AI in social work and social work education. However, this responsibility to think about the ethical implications should not block action and should instead focus on finding workable solutions that enable AI solutions to be applied in ways that respect the ethical standards of the profession.

Overall, the results of this study demonstrate a pattern of cautious recognition of the benefits of AI applications in social work and social work education. The study's participants are conscious of AI's potential benefits for the social work field (Table 1), demand that their departments be more involved in AI education and adoption (Table 2), but simultaneously communicate anxiety about the risks of AI adoption to their employment and the professional values of their profession (Table 3). This combination of factors indicates that Saudi Arabia is in a unique position where a change in direction by social work departments, especially one that moves to directly tackle the situation, instead of avoiding it, would benefit the profession. This change in approach should follow Asakura et al.'s (2020) call for social work educators to expand their involvement in the study of the risks and benefits of AI in social work, and to research and develop ways in which AI-supported systems can support social work practice and education.

4. Conclusion

The findings of this study indicate that although social work students and faculty members generally recognize AI's potential to improve efficiency within practice, facilitate easier development of professional skills, and provide impactful social solutions, they lack confidence in their individual ability to use AI. Moreover, students and faculty consider their ability to use AI tools to be limited and find it difficult to learn about AI. These findings highlight the existing gap between training and education and practical skills in AI use among social workers in Saudi Arabian universities. The study's findings further indicate that social work departments do not teach students AI competencies, despite there being a general expectation for such departments to perform this duty. Practical efforts, such as holding AI workshops and offering structured training, are insufficient. This lack of action by social work departments is creating frustration among students and faculty members who feel that their departments are failing them and the profession.

Finally, the study shows that social work students and faculty members view the adoption of AI as presenting significant risks, particularly the fear of job losses and the erosion of the professional and ethical values of social work. However, these risks can only be addressed if social work departments take the initiative and design curricula that teach AI to students and apply AI in the training of students, after factoring in the risks and challenges associated with this technology. Ultimately, there is an urgent need for social work education in Saudi Arabia to bridge the gap between professionals' awareness of the utility of AI and their skills in practice.

5. Recommendations

The findings from this study highlight the urgent need for social work departments in Saudi Arabia to be more proactive in integrating AI into social work education. Social work departments should assume the responsibility of evaluating the utilization of AI in social work against the values and ethics of the profession. Moreover, social work departments should evaluate the risks involved in introducing AI into social work and design structured curricula that equip students and faculty with AI literacy. The AI education programs ought to enable students to apply AI tools in professional contexts, including their academia. Social work departments must also consider establishing partnerships with national institutions, such as SDAIA, which could help provide resources to facilitate research and the design of effective curricula. Finally, professional

associations for social workers should also help in reducing anxieties about job losses stemming from AI adoption by communicating the current research on this possibility and promoting a balanced approach that stresses AI as a supportive tool for social workers rather than a replacement for them.

Study Contributions

This study contributes to the extant literature on AI and its adoption in social work and social work education by placing the discussion within the Saudi Arabia. More importantly, the study provides empirical evidence on how social work students and faculty members view AI's potential, limitations, and risks. In the process, the study highlights the concerning gap between the awareness of AI's significance and individual practical competency in using AI. The study also provides initial evidence that this gap could be a result of the lack of AI competency education within social work departments in Saudi Arabia.

Study Limitations

While this study introduced new and valuable insights, it is also not free from limitations. First, the study used self-reported data from students and faculty members, which is susceptible conscious and unconscious biases, with participants potentially overstating or understating their knowledge and perceptions of AI. Also, the study utilized a cross-sectional design with perceptions being captured at a single point in time. While these views are important, they are likely to change with time, given how fast AI technology is evolving. Hence, the study's findings only reflect the participants' views at the time of data collection. Lastly, the study combined the views of students and faculty members although they play two separate roles in social work education. Thus, this limited the researcher's ability to compare results from the two groups, which would be beneficial for creating potential interventions.

6. References

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